

BIOMETRIC WATER MARKING BASED ON DISCRETE COSINE TRANSFORM

Vasantha Lakshmi M^{#1}

[#]*Department of Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering, B.M.S.College of Engineering, Bangalore, India*

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Abstract— With the expanded use of biometric technology, securing biometric data has become essential. Most of the time the biometric images are either stored in the raw form or are being transmitted in a channel (insecure channel) as a result there are chances of the biometric data being stolen, faked, or misused. Therefore, it is important to have methods or systems that can secure data such as biometrics. There are various methods to safeguard this biometric data and digital watermarking is one such technique. In this technique, a demographic text can be used as a watermark for the biometric image. The demographic text used as a watermark is encoded in the middle band frequency by interchanging the middle band coefficient pairs of the Discrete Cosine Transform(DCT). Results show that using more than 2 coefficients makes the method more efficient against malicious attacks and image manipulation techniques such as compression. Experimental results show that exchanging more than one pair will make the middle band scheme more robust against malicious attacks along with making it resistant to image manipulation such as compression. Results also show that using this technique does not reduce or manipulate the biometric image and does not decrease the biometric recognition performance.

Keywords— Discrete Cosine Transform, Biometric watermarking, Malicious attack, Authentication

I. INTRODUCTION

Biometrics are measurements of the body and computations of human traits. In computer science, access control and identity are accomplished by biometric authentication, also known as realistic authentication. It is also used to locate people in groups that are being watched.

The distinct, quantifiable traits that are used to identify and categorize people are called biometric identifiers. Physiological traits that are connected to a person's physical attributes, such as body form, are frequently classified as biometric identifiers. Examples include mouse movement, fingerprint, palm veins, face recognition, DNA, palm print, hand geometry, iris recognition, retina, odor/scent, and palm prints. Behavioral traits, such as typing rhythm, movement, signature, behavioral profile, and voice, are connected to a person's pattern of conduct. The latter category of biometrics is referred to as "behavior metrics" by some researchers.

Token-based identity systems, like a passport or driver's license, and knowledge-based identification systems, like a password or personal identifying number, are more conventional methods of access control. Since biometric identifiers are specific to each person, they are more reliable than token- and knowledge-based approaches for confirming identity. However, collecting biometric identifiers raises privacy issues regarding how this data will be used in the future.

Biometrics has long been the focus of future authentication, with the expectation that they will substantially replace other methods of our existing access control and authentication. Two distinct uses for biometric systems are as follows.

Verification is the process of confirming that a person is who they say they are. In the verification mode, the system verifies the user's identity by contrasting the biometric data it has collected with a template that is stored in the database.

Identifying a person is known as Identification. In the identification mode, the system locates the user by looking for a match in all of the database's user templates

As demonstrated in the Figure 1, a biometric system works by first gathering biometric information from a person, extracting features from the data, and then matching the features to a template in the database.

Fig 1 Working of Biometric system

A Biometric Techniques

Whether it is a physical description of a person or, more recently, an image, the usage of biometrics, or especially unique human features, has been around for hundreds of years. Physiological features or behavioral singularities are the two categories under which biometric authentication procedures are categorized. With three levels—high, medium, and low—we compare biometric authentication techniques based on the following six characteristics: security, accuracy, permanence, usability, sufficiency, and prices. The biometric categories are compared in the Table 1 below.

TABLE 1
CATEGORIES OF BIOMETRIC TECHNIQUES

	Security	Accuracy	Permanence	Usability	Costs
Fingerprint Recognition	H	H	M	H	M
Facial Recognition	M	M	M	H	L
Hand Geometry	H	M	M	M	H
Iris	H	H	H	L	H
Retina Identification	H	H	H	L	H
Voice Verification	M	M	L	H	L
Keystroke Dynamics	L	L	L	H	L
Handwritten Signature	M	M	L	M	M

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Watermarking Algorithm

Since a picture may be separated into several frequency bands using watermarking techniques in the DCT domain, it is much simpler to embed the watermarking information in a particular frequency band. According to a recent literature review, the middle-frequency bands are best for embedding watermarks because the low-frequency band carries the majority of the image's visually significant portions while the high-frequency band is vulnerable to removal due to compression and noise attacks on the image. Therefore, placing the watermark in the medium frequency band does not overexpose them to removal through attacks when high-frequency components are the goal, nor does it damage the low frequency, visually essential portions of the image.

The approach ensures that the difference between two mid-band coefficients is positive when the encoded value is 1, which converts one bit of a binary watermark object into one 8 by 8 sub-block of the host image. The two mid-band coefficients are switched if not. As a result, an 8 8 block dimension is taken once the DCT has been applied to the image. As shown in Figure 2, each DCT block is made up of three frequency bands. The lower frequency components of the block are designated by FL, and the higher frequency components are designated by FH. The middle frequency band, FM, was selected for the watermark data embedding. This prevents large changes to the cover image and increases resistance to lossy compression methods that concentrate on the high-frequency components (Hernandez et al., 2000).

Fig 2 DCT Block

B Proposed Algorithm

The host image is converted to a single-channel image and the entire image is divided into 8*8 pixel blocks. Once this is done the watermark image is resized to an appropriate size to fit into the host image, here to 64*64. The grayscale image is used for watermarking that is converted completely to black and white, the pixels having gray levels greater than 127 are converted to 255 i.e. white, and pixels with levels lesser than 127 are converted to 0 i.e. black. The resized black and white watermark image has 4096 pixels which require 4096 different 8*8 host image blocks for them to be embedded into. Each pixel is embedded into an 8*8 pixel block by the following algorithm:

- Now a random 8*8 block of the host image is selected and checked if it has already been used for embedding, if it is not then we proceed further with the embedding process, else pick another block randomly.

- The DCT for the picked block is computed which gives us the frequency domain representation of the image block.

- Now a single DCT value is chosen here at the position (3,3) from the DCT of the 8*8 block. This value is chosen because it lies in the middle frequency DCT coefficient range. Placing the watermark in the medium frequency band does not overexpose them to removal as the high-frequency components are the goal when attacked, nor does it damage the low frequency, visually essential portions of the image.

- This DCT coefficient value is divided by a factor. As we use inbuilt python functions to compute DCT and IDCT, the final images may contain floating points but while saving are converted to integers. This might cause variations while computing DCT during extraction. To overcome this we divide the DCT coefficient by a factor while embedding the watermark pixel.

- Then based on the watermark image pixel value that we are trying to embed we round off the DCT coefficient value to the nearest even or odd value.

- The DCT coefficient after dividing by fact is checked for its magnitude and will be rounded off accordingly. If the quotient is 255, the coefficient will be rounded off to the nearest odd number. If the quotient is 0, then the coefficient will be rounded off to the nearest even number.

- After this the DCT coefficient is multiplied by the factor by which it was previously divided by. This makes it capable of handling a variance of value ranging from +factor/2 to -factor/2 while extracting the watermark, and this won't affect the results.

- Once the pixel value has been embedded, the IDCT for the DCT coefficient block is computed and these computed IDCT blocks are combined together to get the watermarked image and stored in a file.

C Extraction Algorithm

The watermarked image is a 1000*1000 image that has the watermark embedded into it. Similar to the embedding algorithm the watermarked image that is a single channel image is divided into 8*8 pixel blocks and 4096 blocks are chosen to extract the 4096 pixels from the watermark image that were embedded into the host image. The following algorithm is followed for extraction:

- A random 8*8 block of the watermarked image is selected and checked if extraction has already been performed on it, if it is not then we proceed further with the extraction process, else pick another block randomly.
- The DCT for the picked block is computed which gives us the frequency domain representation of the watermarked image block.
- Now the DCT value at the position (3,3) from the DCT of the 8*8 block is chosen as that is the position where the watermark pixel was embedded in the embedding algorithm.
- The value 0.5 is added to the DCT coefficient value at position (3,3). As we use inbuilt python functions to compute DCT and IDCT, there might be variations in values while computing DCT from the saved watermark image, the variance can occur by a factor of 0.5. To overcome this we add this 0.5 value to the DCT coefficient and further divide it by a factor.
- Based on the value of this computed coefficient being even or odd we extract grayscale values of 0 if the coefficient is even or else 255 is taken.
- These grayscale values are placed into an image array based on the block chosen for extraction.
- The image array is then saved as a .jpg image which can be viewed to see the extracted watermark.

III.IMPLEMENTATION RESULT

The finger print and the text image of a particular person generated is given in Figure 3.

Fingerprint image as input

Text image as input

Manoj
1235468754
543546
54634

Fig 3 Fingerprint and text image as input

The image after watermarking and the extracted text of the image is given in Figure 4.

Image after watermarking

Fig 4 Watermarked image and extracted text

The rest of the paper discuss the various attacks on the algorithm

- **Geometric attacks:** Geometric attack is when we try to change the size of an image and then try to extract the embedded watermark. Here, noise is added to the watermarked image as given in Figure 5.

a. Scaling down of image

Extracted watermark

Manoj
1235468754
543546
54634

b. Scaling up the image

Extracted watermark

Manoj
1235468754
543546
54634

Fig 5 Results of Geometric attacks

- **Signal-based Attacks:** Here, the image is subjected to pass through the filter . Figure 6 describes the result when the image is passed through median filter.

Fig 6 Image passed through Median Filter

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Since the world around us is moving fast toward digital technology, internet banking, and electronic transactions, biometrics are the only way to approve or verify a transfer or transaction hence it is really important to safeguard the biometric information as, if fallen in malicious hands it may lead to a loss of property or even lead to loss of lives. There are many methods to safeguard the biometrics and one such method is digital watermarking which is basically embedding a binary image (watermark) into a biometric image (host image) using an embedding algorithm, the embedding of the watermark image is done in the middle frequency band of the host image. The frequency bands are obtained when DCT is applied to the host image. The reason the embedding is done only in the middle frequency is because the high-frequency band is usually susceptible to various noise attacks and hacks hence it is pretty useless if it is embedded here and in the lower frequency band, the important parts of the image are present hence any embedding done here will result in deformation of the host image, hence the most suitable frequency is the middle frequency band as it is somewhat resistible to various noise attacks and any embedding done here doesn't deform the host image and watermark can be obtained after applying the extraction algorithm to the watermarked host image, in result analysis, we can see the watermark images extracted after various attacks to watermarked host image. In this way, this method is used to safeguard biometric data or information.

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